

ΔT , contrary to expectation (Table 2). This may be because when these acids are added to the basic TEA-Water mixture, it is the salt produced, triethylammonium trichloroacetate or triethylammonium nitrate, which decides the sign of ΔT .

Thus the present study reveals a systematic effect of ion-size on the PST of the TEA-Water system. Electrolytes of smaller ions give negative ΔT , while larger ions give positive ΔT . This size effect may be referred to making or breaking of structure in water¹⁹⁻²¹, which in turn results in negative or positive ΔT , as per the ionic sizes.

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Synthesis and Study of Anthelmintic Activity of Some Newer Benzimidazoles

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COMPOUNDS containing benzimidazole nucleus have been reported to possess a wide spectrum of anthelmintic activity. Several benzimidazole derivatives e.g., thiabendazole, mebendazole, flubendazole etc are used clinically¹ for the eradication of helminthic infections. The incorporation of substituted isothiocyanates in benzimidazole nucleus results in an increase in the anthelmintic activity². In continuation of our interest on the search of new anthelmintic compounds, we have synthesized benzimidazolyl thiosemicarbazides and screened them for their anthelmintic activity against *H. nana*.

Experimental

All the compounds were routinely checked by tlc on Silica Gel 'G' using benzene/methanol as solvent system, ir spectrum of compounds 9 and 19 was determined using a Perkin-Elmer Model 137. The melting points were taken in open capillary and are uncorrected.

1. *2-Benzimidazole acetic acid hydrazide*: It was prepared from ethyl 2-benzimidazole acetate following the method of Ralph³ et al.

2. *1-N-2-(2'-acetobenzimidazolyl)-4-aryl thiosemicarbazides*: 2-Benzimidazolyl acetic acid hydrazide (0.01 mole) was taken in dry benzene and appropriate substituted phenyl isothiocyanate (0.01 mole) was added to it. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 4 hrs; on cooling a crystalline solid separated out, it was filtered and washed with petroleum ether to remove excess of isothiocyanate and recrystallized from ethanol (50%). Details of the compounds are listed in Table 1.

Compound 9 showed characteristic bands for C=O (1660 cm⁻¹) C=N (1610 cm⁻¹) and C=S (1050 cm⁻¹) in the ir spectrum.

3. *1-N-2-(2'-ethyl benzimidazolyl)-4-aryl thiosemicarbazides*: 1-N-(2-acetobenzimidazolyl)-4-aryl thiosemicarbazide (1 mole) was suspended in dry ether (100 ml), to this solution LAH (2 mole) was added slowly in 30 minutes and left overnight. The unreacted LAH was decomposed, filtered and usual

* Part of this work will be incorporated in the Ph.D. Thesis of (Miss) Garima Sathi.

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TABLE 1—1-N-2-(2'-ACETOBENZIMIDAZOLYL)-4-ARYL THIOSEMICARBAZIDES AND THEIR ANTHELMINTIC ACTIVITY

Compd. No.	R	Molecular formula	m.p. °C	Yield %	Mice survived	Mice clear from infection	% clear	Activity	LD ₅₀ mg/kg i.p.
1.	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₅ OS	105	80	5/5	2/5	40	Active	
2.	<i>m</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₅ OS	117	85	5/5	3/5	60	Active	>2000
3.	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₅ O ₂ S	152	70	5/5	3/5	60	Active	>2000
4.	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₅ O ₂ S	130	80	5/5	0/5	0	Inactive	
5.	<i>m</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₅ O ₂ S	121	75	4/5	0/5	0	Inactive	
6.	<i>o</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₅ OSCl	167	70	5/5	2/5	40	Active	
7.	<i>m</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₅ OSCl	125	75	5/5	4/5	80	Active	>2000
8.	<i>m</i> -FC ₆ H ₄	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₅ OSF	152	80	5/5	0/5	0	Inactive	
9.	C ₆ H ₁₁	C ₁₆ H ₂₁ N ₅ OS	142	90	4/5	0/4	0	Inactive	
10.	C ₂ H ₅	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ N ₅ OS	120	85	5/5	2/5	40	Active	

Analysis of N within ±0.4 of theoretical value.

TABLE 2—1-N-2-(2'ETHYL BENZIMIDAZOLYL)-4-ARYL THIOSEMICARBAZIDES AND THEIR ANTHELMINTIC ACTIVITY

Compd. No.	R	Molecular formula	m.p. °C	Yield %	Mice survived	Mice clear from infection	% clear	Activity	ALD ₅₀ mg/kg i.p.
11.	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ N ₅ S	150	30	5/5	3/5	60	Active	>2000
12.	<i>m</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ N ₅ S	148	20	5/5	2/5	40	Active	
13.	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ N ₅ OS	122	35	5/5	1/5	20	Active	
14.	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ N ₅ OS	116	30	4/5	0/5	0	Inactive	
15.	<i>m</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ N ₅ OS	182	35	4/5	0/5	0	Inactive	
16.	<i>o</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ N ₅ SCl	125	40	5/5	3/5	60	Active	>2000
17.	<i>m</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ N ₅ SCl	165	35	5/5	3/5	60	Active	>2000
18.	<i>m</i> -FC ₆ H ₄	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ N ₅ SF	124	30	5/5	2/5	40	Active	
19.	C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₆ H ₂₃ N ₅ S	181	40	5/5	2/5	40	Active	
20.	C ₂ H ₅	C ₁₃ H ₁₇ N ₅ S	142	40	5/5	3/5	60	Active	>2000

Analysis of N within ±0.4 of theoretical values.

work up afforded a solid which was crystallized from alcohol. The compounds thus prepared are listed in Table 2.

Compound 19 showed characteristic bands for NH (3200 cm⁻¹) C=N (1610 cm⁻¹) and C=S (1050 cm⁻¹) in ir spectrum. As expected carbonyl peak was absent.

Biological studies: The *in vivo* anthelmintic screening was done in mice, following the method of Steward⁴ *et al.*

The anthelmintic evaluation was done on the basis of mice cleared of infection and the percentage calculated. The compounds were administered at a dose of 500 mg/kg orally.

The ALD₅₀ was done in mice following the method of Smith⁵ *et al* at a dose of 2000 mg/kg i.p. The results are given in Tables 1 and 2.

Results and Discussion

All the compounds were screened for anthelmintic activity against *H. nana* in mice.

Compounds 1, 2, 3, 6 and 10 showed moderate activity. Maximum activity was shown by compound 7, whereas compounds 4, 5, 8 and 9 were devoid of activity.

In the corresponding reduced compounds the activity increased in compounds 11, 16, 18, 19 and 20. In compounds 12, 13 and 17 a decrease in activity was shown, no change in the activity was observed in compounds 14 and 15.

The approximate ALD₅₀ values of active compounds (activity >60%) was determined in mice and was found to be >2000 mg/kg i.p.

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Potential Carcinostats : Synthesis of New

Azo Coumarins*

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COMPOUNDS bearing azo groups are known to exhibit bacterostatic^{1,2} and anticancerous³ activity. Some azo compounds have been reported to inhibit tumor growth in mice and rats⁴. Though vast amount of work has been done on coumarins^{5,6,7}, reference on the synthesis of coumarins using azosalicylaldehydes and malonanilic acids have not come to notice.

In the present investigation 5-phenylazo salicylaldehyde or 5-*m*-toluylazosalicylaldehyde have been condensed with malonanilic acids in absence or presence of trace of piperidine or pyridine and the coumarins(I) and the Schiff bases(II) have been obtained. Maximum yield of the coumarins has been observed when piperidine was used as the condensing agents. Schiff bases were formed in very low yield when piperidine was used as condensing agent. The yield of Schiff base was higher when condensations were done in absence of condensing agents, where the yield of coumarins declined.

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Data concerning new coumarins and Schiff bases are set out in Table 1. Schiff bases were formed in five condensations. Separation of coumarins from Schiff base was done by fractional crystallisation from ethanol, in which the coumarins are very sparingly soluble.

TABLE 1

Compound*	AZO-COUMARINS(I)		Yield (%)	m.p. (°C)
	R	Colour		
1.	H	Darkbrown	17.4	260
2.	CH ₃ (<i>o</i>)	Lightbrown	09.2	270(d)
3.	CH ₃ (<i>m</i>)	Brown	09.2	285(d)
4.	CH ₃ (<i>p</i>)	Brown	09.2	280(d)
5.	Cl(<i>o</i>)	Brown	12.4	320(d)
6.	Cl(<i>m</i>)	Lightbrown	19.05	320(d)
7.	Cl(<i>p</i>)	Lightbrown	30.6	320(d)
8.	OCH ₃ (<i>o</i>)	Lightyellow	15.7	290(d)
9.	OCH ₃ (<i>m</i>)	Brown	41.8	305(d)
10.	OCH ₃ (<i>p</i>)	Darkbrown	30.4	298(d)
	Schiff bases(II)			
11.	CH ₃ (<i>o</i>)	Yellow	10.9	111
12.	Cl(<i>o</i>)	Lightbrown	16.0	120
13.	Cl(<i>m</i>)	Lightbrown	07.4	138
14.	Cl(<i>p</i>)	Brown	20.8	131
15.	OCH ₃ (<i>o</i>)	Lightyellow	13.00	97

* All compounds analysed well for C, H and N values.

The azo coumarins dyed cotton, silk, wool and polyester fibers in yellow or orange shades, which were fast to light on washing.

Potentiality of the new azo coumarins as carcinostats is currently being assessed.

Experimental

M. ps. are uncorrected. 5-phenylazo salicylaldehyde⁸ and malonanilic acids^{9,10} were prepared by the methods reported in the literature.

Preparations of 5-m-toluylazo salicylaldehyde: *m*-Toluidine (4.5 ml) was dissolved in hydrochloric acid (28 ml; 6*M*) and diazotised using sodium nitrite (4 g).

Cold solution of salicylaldehyde (5 g) in aqueous sodium hydroxide (40 ml; 2*N*) was added slowly with continuous stirring to *m*-toluyl diazonium chloride. The precipitate was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol/acetic acid mixture (1:1), Yield, 6.0 g (62.5%), m.p. 125°.

Found N: 11.30; C₁₄H₁₂N₂O₂ requires N, 11.66%.

Condensations of azo salicylaldehyde with malonanilic acid, formation of 6-(phenylazo) coumarin-3-carboxy anilide: Malonanilic acid (0.900 g; 0.005 mole) and 5-phenyl azosalicylaldehyde (1.30 g; 0.005 mole) were mixed and heated in an oil bath for